

PHOTORAMA, a new European technology route to recover and recycle all the materials components from End-of-life PV panels.

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Abstract — PHOTORAMA is an integrated new technology for the completely recovery and recycling of PV module and its components. PHOTORAMA works in that direction by developing an innovative and eco-friendly process which comprises disassembly, delamination and metal recovery steps. PHOTORAMA represents a radical innovation with respect to currently available solutions to treat end-of-life PV modules; efficiency and effectiveness of the exploitation of secondary raw materials from end-of-life PV panels can be significantly increased by the PHOTORAMA solution. The project results can overcome technical and market barriers in the recovery of Critical Raw Materials from PV panels and thus the project will make a vital contribution to the exploitation of urban mines. The project has the potential to significantly change the landscape of the photovoltaic through improved circularity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic (PV) panels are an important component of the ongoing drive toward decarbonised energy generation. Energy production from PV panels has been increasing steadily since the early 2000s and is expected to reach 8,519 GW worldwide in 2050 [1]. However, PV panels only have a lifespan of nearly 30 years [2] and the mass of end-of-life panels worldwide is expected to reach between 2 and 8 million tonnes by 2030 [2], with currently no viable outlet and actually recovering metals from spent PV cells is a major economic and environmental challenge.

The methods currently available for the recovery of materials deriving from photovoltaic waste are energetically expensive and have an impact from an environmental point of view. The development of innovative and eco-sustainable technologies for the recovery of materials deriving from photovoltaic systems at the end of their life, allows the optimization of the global economy of the production process of new panels starting from recycled materials and the obtaining of benefits in the reduction of pollution, in the protection and preservation of the environment. The correct management of photovoltaic waste allows, in fact, the minimization of the volume and

quantity of materials sent to landfills, the recovery and recycling of useful and reusable materials (glass, aluminium, silver, copper, semiconductors, etc.), the reduction of the consumption of raw materials and energy and the positive closure of the energy balance of the entire life cycle of a PV module. The foremost goal of PHOTORAMA (PHOTOvoltaic waste management – advanced Technologies for recOvery and recycling of secondary Raw Materials from end-of-life modules) is to develop and demonstrate innovative solutions dedicated to Raw Material recycling from complex multi-layers End of Life products aiming at minimizing waste and achieving high RM recovery rates. The implementation of a full-management PILOT LINE will address low-carbon recycling of PV modules crystalline Silicon (c-Si), Thin Film CIGS-CIS to recover the critical and precious metals: Si, In, Ga, Ag.

II. OBJECTIVES

Since the last decades, Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) have been drastically increasing in Europe, particularly for recent technologies such as Photovoltaic (PV) devices [3]. These products are designed as complex sandwiches, which make the recovery of the critical (Si, In, Ga) and precious (Ag) raw materials encapsulated in the layers extremely challenging.

The overall objective of PHOTORAMA is to draw up a profitable and sustainable circular value chain that will lead to a carbon neutral PV industry. PHOTORAMA will develop and demonstrate the industrial prospective of recycling solutions to recover and recycle all the materials components from End-of-life PV panels. A complementary consortium of 14 European companies and research institutes has built the framework of PHOTORAMA as follow:

(1) The implementation of a pilot line with the development of innovative processes and technologies from TRL4-5 to TRL7 to establish a sound recycling scheme to increase

significantly resource efficiency with decisive cost-cutting solutions. The implementation of automated disassembly and sandwich opening as layer separation enabling high-recovery (> 95%) of secondary raw materials: Ag, Si and In, Ga from EoL PV panels (crystalline silicon & thin films)

(2) The full-circularity approach emphasised from collection to marketable new products from Si, In, Ga, Ag, glass mainly for PV manufacturing.

(3) The demonstration of the business viability and attractiveness of its technological solutions as one of the most competitive perspective for PV recycling.

The implementation of PHOTORAMA recycling scheme would unlock already more than 100,000 tons of valuable secondary raw materials by 2030.

The challenge of recycling regarding EoL PV modules is illustrated by the figure beside (Fig.1).

This shows on the left the dramatic outcomes of current recycling practices based on crushing/ shredding processes. The mixed fractions are mostly landfilled or eventually re-directed to very low-value applications, which is noticeably identified as down-cycling. On the right side of the Figure 1, as a complete turnover: the novel approach of PHOTORAMA highlighting the huge benefits in terms of materials recovery, thus in terms of revenues, which could be brought by innovative solutions.

Fig. 1. PHOTORAMA up-cycling scheme.

The first step of the new technology starts with a high automation degree for disassembly to make the whole scheme profitable and safer compared to the current practices. Secondly, innovative layer separation will enable the access to the valuable secondary RM encapsulated in the components layers. Thirdly, new green metal extraction technologies will lead to efficient recovery of precious and critical metals (Si, Ag, In, Ga) from solar cells.

The whole scheme here will result in up-cycling with high-value recovery of materials: aluminum from the frame, glass

and polymers from the top and bottom sheets and metals: Cu, Si, Ag or In, Ga from the solar cells' layer. Furthermore, the pilot line will be exploited to recycle PV manufacturing wastes (glass, solar cells) and test eco-designed PV devices underway in order to fulfil and demonstrate its exhaustive and complete capacity to produce secondary RM from waste.

III. CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGY

The overall concept of PHOTORAMA is to develop and demonstrate a systemic approach taking into account the whole PV value chain and all the stakeholders involved. Figure 2 shows the concept as a circular loop: from the collection to the production of secondary RM and their reintroduction to RM industries as new materials and new products.

Fig. 2. PHOTORAMA concept.

The strategy is to look at the entire picture and draw up a scheme for PV recycling taking into account technical, economic, environmental and social dimensions. The novel and comprehensive approach of recycling has been defined to recover critical and precious secondary RM. The scheme includes all needed interrelated successive steps to set up a -full management- pilot line illustrated by the left part of the Figure 2 in the section Recycling: Auto Disassembly of external components such as frame, electric supply, junction box to reduce the cost of manual labour; Smart Separation to open flat sandwich structures to access the critical and precious RM encapsulated in the component layers; Innovative recovery of critical, precious RM from sandwich layers by using new and environmentally friendly extraction routes. In order to close the loop by transforming waste into new products, all fractions of PV EoL components will be either directly re-used, recycled to build new PV panels or as RM feedstock for suitable industries.

IV. RESULTS AND INNOVATIONS

The innovation route of PHOTORAMA is designed to gather the most efficient, cost-effective and environmentally friendly technologies to set up a pilot line that can fully-manage EoL PV waste. It is defined from three main steps:

(1) Automation development: it will be undertaken to perform the disassembly of components such as aluminum frame, electric supply and junction box. The innovative automation will enable the processing of all kinds of PV panel size (1.65-2 m²) and weight (16-22kg) and treat about 1000tons/year. A sorting unit using X-Ray will enable the selection of the modules depending on solar cells' technology (c-Si, CIGS-CIS, CdTe).

(2) Smart separation of PV panels: through the innovative approach of layer separation, PHOTORAMA will implement two technologies beyond state of the art that are more efficient (suitable to high volume) and more ecological (low-energy process). The clean separation of component layers will improve material recovery by providing uncontaminated fractions (glass, solar cells, polymer).

Mechanical separation. A completely new approach based on diamond wire cutting [4] has been proven by reliable experiments will demonstrate the separation of the glass sheet from solar cells & of the back-sheet. It will display an efficient route to recover all valuable material components.

Super critical Fluid process. As a novel advanced delamination solution for PV recycling is based on pioneering treatments coupling CO₂/H₂O fluids [5]. Experiments have demonstrated partial to total delamination of PV module samples. provide a major improvement over classical methods with no waste generated (CO₂, water recycled in the process loop) and without any loss of material.

(3) Metal extraction

The metal extraction from the active part on pv panel is done via Ionic Liquid (IL) and Methane Sulfonic Acid (MSA).

For c-Si modules a pioneering iono-metallurgical route to recover Ag without using concentrated mineral acids has been developed and efficient Ag extraction (ratio >95%) from solid waste has been demonstrated[6]. After dissolution, electrodeposition has been successfully performed to recover Ag under metallic form. The remaining silicon fraction will be recovered at metallurgical grade. This groundbreaking solution will enable high-ratio and high-purity metal recovery using a green solvent recyclable in the loop of the treatment cycle.

For thin film modules a MSA solution is used to recover In and Ga from CIGS thin film solar cells. PV cell's layers are completely dissolved in a mixture of a methane sulfonic acid and a diluted oxidizing agent. The high solubility of In and Ga enables dissolution and then concentration processes to recover 98-100% from material waste. In the case of heterojunction both indium-containing ITO layer and silver contacts are

dissolved within the MSA system. This solution is to be treated electrochemically in order to isolate the metals (In, Ag). Most of the chemicals products are entirely recovered in the process loop.

V. CONCLUSIONS

PHOTORAMA will demonstrate tomorrow's industrial solutions enabling the recovery and the production of secondary RM. The technologies have been carefully selected considering their environmental impacts, using low-energy process, promoting products' process re-use with chemical processes. On a larger scale, the metal production will prevent the extraction of primary RM and the loss of materials from landfill. Development of full technological low-carbon solutions to set-up the pilot line with the technology development from TRL4-5 with the evident and technical potential to reach the TRL7 maturity. All the details on PHOTORAMA project are in <https://www.photorama-project.eu/>.

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